

A novel flavone-based fluorescent probe for hydrazine detection in aqueous, soil and cell environments

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ABSTRACT

Hydrazine, a colourless and highly reactive chemical, is commonly used in various fields such as industry, agriculture, and medicine. While it serves important roles, it is also highly toxic and can cause severe health issues, including cancer and neurological disorders. Providing a simple, reliable, and practical approach to monitoring hydrazine levels will be imperative due to its essential roles. Herein, we report a novel flavone-based fluorescent probe, ARYA, which exhibits a “turn-on” fluorescence response with high selectivity and sensitivity (LOD = 71 nM). The probe effectively detects hydrazine in aqueous solutions, soil, and living cells, providing a practical and versatile tool for environmental and biological monitoring. These results highlight ARYA as a promising platform for rapid and sensitive hydrazine detection in complex media.

1. Introduction

Hydrazine is a crucial chemical compound widely utilized in industry, agriculture, aerospace and fuel cells due to its significant features such as alkalinity, reducibility, and flammability (Fan et al., 2022; Jung et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2014). Although it is essential for rocket propulsion systems and serves as an oxygen scavenger in boiler water treatment, there are significant health and environmental issues due to its high toxicity and possible carcinogenic effects (Jin et al., 2015; Oguz et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2023). Hydrazine is classified by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) as a Group B2 probable human carcinogen, with a threshold value of 10 ppb (0.31 μM), due to its ability to be readily absorbed through ingestion, skin contact, or inhalation, causing damage to the liver, kidneys, central nervous system, and respiratory system (Hydrazine/Hydrazine Sulfate (CASRN 302-01-2) | IRIS | US EPA, 1988). In addition, its higher water solubility leads to the formation of hydrazine hydrate, which can irritate the respiratory system at low concentrations, whereas it can cause neurological problems and irreversible organ damage at high concentrations (Oguz et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2023). Furthermore, hydrazine can bioaccumulate throughout the food chain due to water and soil pollution caused by leaks during production, transportation, or disposal (Zeng et al., 2023). Since hundreds of thousands of tons are produced worldwide each year, developing accurate, efficient, and selective hydrazine detection

techniques is crucial.

Numerous traditional analytical techniques, such as liquid chromatography (Song et al., 2017), solid phase extraction (Gionfriddo et al., 2014), surface-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (Gu and Camden, 2015), and electrochemical analysis (Tajik et al., 2020) have been documented until now. However, these methods require prolonged analysis time, complex sample processing and proficient staff for data interpretation. On the other hand, fluorescent probes are remarkable because they provide a more straightforward methodology, high sensitivity and selectivity, real-time monitoring, unique stability and biocompatibility. A series of fluorescent molecules, including rhodamine (Horzum et al., 2016; Iyer et al., 2023; Lalitha and Velmathi, 2024; Suna et al., 2022), BODIPY (Kolemen and Akkaya, 2018; Nguyen et al., 2021; Suna, et al., 2023a, 2023b), fluorescein (Karakus et al., 2019; S et al., 2021; Suna et al., 2025; Verma et al., 2024), triphenylamine (Erdemir et al., 2022a; Karak et al., 2022), tetraphenylethylene (Erdemir et al., 2022b; Zhu et al., 2025), and thienothiophene (Fernandes et al., 2022; Suna et al., 2024; Suna, et al., 2023a, 2023b), are commonly used as signal-reporting units. Besides these popular fluorescent molecules, flavonols — a subgroup of flavonoids — have drawn great interest due to their outstanding photophysical features and biological significance. They are widely utilized in fluorescence-based sensing applications because they can produce dual emission bands and large Stokes shifts due to their excited-state intramolecular proton transfer (ESIPT)

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properties (Gu et al., 2023; He et al., 2020; Karakuş et al., 2016; Li et al., 2021; Qin et al., 2021; Sedgwick et al., 2018). Numerous studies in the literature, including both ESIPT-based and non-ESIPT hydrazine probes, have been reported for hydrazine detection. However, in addition to limitations such as low fluorescence quantum yield, slow response time, and cross-sensitivity, many of these systems also require multi-step synthesis procedures. (Fan et al., 2022; Jin et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2022; Qin et al., 2021; Xiao et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2016). Therefore, there is an urgent need to design and develop new probes to handle the above-mentioned drawbacks.

In this study, we developed a new hydrazine (N₂H₄) responsive probe (ARYA) based on 3-hydroxyflavone ESIPT fluorophore that exhibited outstanding sensing abilities, such as superior selectivity and high sensitivity with a very low limit of detection (LOD). It can detect N₂H₄ not only in aqueous solution but also in living cell medium. As a result of these findings, we utilized ARYA to successfully determine the trace amount of N₂H₄ in real water and soil environments.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Instruments and materials

2'-Hydroxyacetophenone (≥98%, Sigma Aldrich), 4-Mercaptobenzoic acid (≥98%, Sigma Aldrich), 4-Nitrothalonitrile (≥95%, Abcr), benzaldehyde (≥95%, Abcr), N,N'-Dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) (≥98%, Sigma Aldrich), 4-(Dimethylamino)pyridine (DMAP) (≥98%, Sigma Aldrich), (≥97%, Sigma-Aldrich), dichloromethane anhydrous (≥99.9%, Sigma-Aldrich), ethanol (≥99.8%, Sigma-Aldrich), dichloromethane (≥99.8%, Sigma-Aldrich), Dimethyl sulfoxide (≥99.8%, Sigma-Aldrich). All water-soluble sulfate, nitrate, or chloride anion-cation salts (≥95%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were obtained on a Varian VNMRJ 600 NMR spectrometer. High-Resolution Mass Spec-trometry (HRMS) analysis was recorded on a Waters SYNAPT G1 MS (Waters, USA). Ultraviolet–visible absorption measurements were carried out using a Shimadzu 1900i, and fluorescence emission spectra were recorded with a Varian Cary Eclipse fluorescence spectrophotometer.

2.2. Preparation of solutions for UV–Vis and fluorescence assays

A stock solution of ARYA (1 mM) was initially dissolved in DMSO. Separate 20 mM stock solutions of cation/anion salts and other analytes were prepared in ultrapure water (UPW). For each measurement, other analyte solutions were introduced into 2 mL of ARYA solution using a micropipette. The working ARYA concentration for both UV–Vis and fluorescence analysis was adjusted to 20 μM in 4:1 (v/v) DMSO:PBS buffer at pH 7.4. Fluorescence data were recorded in quartz cuvettes with a 1 cm optical path. The emission range was set between 450–650 nm upon excitation at 435 nm, with both excitation and emission slit widths maintained at 10 nm. All measurements were performed in triplicate for reproducibility.

2.3. Cell imaging

Human A549 lung adenocarcinoma cells were cultured in DMEM supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS), incubated at 37°C in a humidified 5% CO₂ atmosphere. Cells were seeded into 6-well plates and maintained for 24 h. Before treatment, they were washed with 0.1 M PBS, followed by a 20 min incubation at 37°C with ARYA (20 μM). After rinsing three times with PBS, cells were incubated for an additional 20 min with N₂H₄ (50 μM) under the same conditions and washed again. DAPI was then added, incubated for 10 min at 37°C, and removed by triple PBS washing. Fluorescence images were subsequently captured using a fluorescence microscope. The respective excitation/emission wavelengths were 360/525 nm for ARYA (to evaluate interaction with N₂H₄) and 360/460 nm for DAPI.

2.4. Analysis of real water samples

Recovery tests were designed to detect N₂H₄ in drinking water, tap water, and wastewater. Calibration curves for each water type were generated by adding known N₂H₄ concentrations to evaluate matrix effects. Spiked samples containing predetermined N₂H₄ levels were analyzed with ARYA, and quantification was based on fluorescence intensity changes. Each experiment was repeated at least three times, and recovery rates were determined by comparing detected and spiked concentrations.

2.5. Soil sample preparation and analysis

Clay, sandy, and field soils were collected, oven-dried at 80°C for 24 h, and used without further purification. For simulated contamination, 200 mg of each soil was placed into glass vials and treated with 200 μM N₂H₄ solution. After 2 h incubation at room temperature, 2 mL of sensing medium containing 40 μM ARYA was added. Samples were shaken for 30 min to ensure thorough mixing and then left undisturbed for 15 min to allow sedimentation (or short centrifugation). The clear supernatant was examined under 365 nm UV light for visual detection of N₂H₄ in soil environments (Eldem et al., 2025).

2.6. Synthesis of ARYA

Compounds FL–OH and CN–TBA were synthesized by following previously reported procedures (Karakuş et al., 2019, Özçelik et al., 2023). FL–OH (100 mg, 0.42 mmol) and 4-((3,4-dicyanophenyl)thio)benzoic acid (CN–TBA) (129.4 mg, 0.46 mmol) were dissolved in dry CH₂Cl₂ (10 mL) under inert atmosphere. To this solution, dicyclohexylcarbodiimide (DCC) (86.6 mg, 0.42 mmol) and 4-dimethylaminopyridine (DMAP) (5.1 mg, 0.042 mmol) were added and the reaction mixture was stirred overnight at room temperature. Following completion, the solvent was removed by reducing the pressure, and the resulting crude product was extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (three times). The combined organic fractions were dried over anhydrous MgSO₄, filtered and concentrated. Purification via column chromatography using a 2:1

Scheme 1. Synthetic pathway of ARYA.

Fig. 1. (a) Absorption and (b) emission spectra of ARYA (20 μM) in the absence and presence of N_2H_4 (10 equiv.) in 4:1 DMSO:PBS (v/v) at pH 7.4.

hexane-ethyl acetate mixture afforded ARYA as a yellowish-white solid (142.9 mg, 68% yield). ^1H NMR (600 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 8.29 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 1H), 8.26 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 7.92 (d, $J = 6.5$ Hz, 2H), 7.76 (t, $J = 6.0$ Hz, 1H), 7.67 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.63–7.58 (m, 4H), 6.85, 7.54–7.45 (m, 5H), 6.85. ^{13}C NMR (150 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 172.1, 163.1, 156.8, 155.9, 145.7, 137.1, 134.6, 134.4, 134.1, 134.0, 133.7, 132.3, 132.2, 132.0, 131.7, 131.2, 131.1, 130.1, 130.0, 129.0, 128.8, 128.5, 126.4, 125.6, 123.8, 118.4, 117.0, 115.4, 114.9, 113.0 HRMS (ESI): m/z : Calcd. for ($\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$) $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$: 501.09090 found, 501.0909. FTIR: ν (cm^{-1}): 3513, 3305, 2953, 2928, 2851, 2233, 1739, 1621, 1580, 1466, 1387, 1238, 1190, 1148, 1057, 1011, 902, 824, 758, 694, 521.

3. Results and discussion

In this section, the sensing behavior of ARYA toward hydrazine is discussed by considering solvent effects, pH dependence, photophysical properties, and the underlying reaction mechanism. The observed fluorescence response and analytical performance are interpreted in the context of previously reported hydrazine fluorescent probes, with emphasis on sensitivity, selectivity, response time, and applicability in environmental and biological matrices. ARYA was synthesized in a single-step coupling reaction between FL-OH and CN-TBA using DCC and DMAP at room temperature, affording the target product in 68% isolated yield (Scheme 1). The molecule retained its structural integrity

during purification, and its identity was confirmed unambiguously by ^1H NMR, ^{13}C NMR, and high-resolution mass spectrometry, with full characterization data provided in the Supporting Information.

Due to the highly polar nature of the probe, we selected DMSO as the organic solvent in our sensing media. Polar aprotic solvents such as DMSO are frequently employed in hydrazine sensing systems to ensure sufficient solubility and to promote nucleophilic reaction pathways (Fan et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2016). The combination of water with other solvents such as ethanol and acetonitrile adversely affects sensing capability (Fig. S1), which is consistent with an earlier report showing that protic solvents may suppress fluorescence recovery or slow down hydrolysis-triggered responses (Zhang et al., 2016). Among various solvent combinations of DMSO and water (e.g. 9:1, 8:2, 7:3 etc.), a mixture of DMSO- H_2O (4:1, v/v) was selected as the most effective working media for N_2H_4 sensing (Fig. S2). In fluorescence sensor studies, pH changes in the working environment directly affect the sensing system. At the same time, pH is a significant parameter for further applications. Therefore, we initially identified the appropriate buffer solution. HEPES, phosphate buffer (PB) and phosphate buffer saline (PBS) were tested and DMSO: PBS combination was selected as the most suitable sensing media (Fig. S3). The fluorescence response of ARYA was examined over a broad pH range to assess its stability under physiologically relevant conditions. The probe exhibited excellent stability between pH 2 and 11 and continued its ability to detect N_2H_4 within the

Fig. 2. (a) Fluorescence titration spectra of ARYA (20 μM) in 4:1 DMSO:PBS (v/v) at pH 7.4 in the presence of N_2H_4 (0–10 equiv.) (b) Fluorescence intensity changes depending on mole equivalents of $\text{N}_2\text{H}_4 = 0$ –20 equiv.

Fig. 3. (a) Fluorescence intensities of ARYA (20 μ M) in 4:1 DMSO:PBS (v/v) at pH 7.4 at λ_{\max} = 535 nm in the presence of N₂H₄ (10 equiv.) and other metal ions (25 equiv.) 1, K⁺; 2, Na⁺; 3, Li²⁺; 4, Ag⁺; 5, Hg²⁺; 6, Ba²⁺, 7, Ca²⁺; 8, Cd²⁺; 9, Co²⁺; 10, Cu²⁺; 11, Mg²⁺, 12, Mn²⁺; 13, Ni²⁺; 14, Pb²⁺; 15, Zn²⁺; 16, Al³⁺; 17, Fe³⁺; 18, Ce³⁺; (b) Fluorescence intensities of ARYA (20 μ M) in 4:1 DMSO:PBS (v/v) at pH 7.4 at λ_{\max} = 535 nm in the presence of N₂H₄ (10 equiv.) and other analytes (25 equiv.) 1, N₂H₄; 2, ethanolamine; 3, cyclohexylamine; 4, hydroxylamine; 5, butylamine; 6, dimethylamine; 7, trimethylamine; 8, n-methyldiisopropylamine; 9, DMF; 10, pyridine; 11, tribenzylamine; 12, triphenylamine; 13, urea; 14, aniline; 15, Br⁻; 16, Cl⁻; 17, F⁻; 18, AcO⁻; 19, ClO⁻; 20, CN⁻; 21, NO₂⁻; 22, NO₃⁻; 23, H₂S; 24, CO₃²⁻; 25, SO₃²⁻; 26, SO₄²⁻; 27, S₂O₃²⁻; 28, PO₄³⁻.

range of pH 3–11. Such a wide operational pH window compares favorably with other reported hydrazine probes (Wang et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2016). These results highlight ARYA's potential for diverse biological applications; therefore, a sensing medium at pH 7.4 was employed in all subsequent cell imaging experiments (Fig. S4).

The optical behaviour of ARYA in the absence and presence of N₂H₄ was examined under physiological pH conditions using both UV–Vis and fluorescence spectroscopy. As expected for ESIPT-type fluorophores, masking the hydroxyl group effectively quenched the emission, rendering ARYA (Φ_F = 0.001) both colourless and non-fluorescent in a DMSO:PBS mixture at pH 7.4. Fluorescence suppression via ESIPT inhibition has been extensively reported as an effective strategy for designing turn-on probes with low background signals (Liu et al., 2014; Fan et al., 2022; Jin et al., 2015; Xiao et al., 2024) Upon exposure to N₂H₄, a rapid hydrolysis reaction occurred, resulting in the removal of the protective group and the restoration of the free hydroxyl functionality. This structural transformation reactivated the ESIPT process, giving rise to a pronounced "turn-on" response in both absorption and emission profiles. Hydrazine-triggered deprotection reactions have been widely exploited in probe design due to their high selectivity toward N₂H₄ over other nucleophiles (Liu et al., 2014; Fan et al., 2022; Jin et al., 2015; Xiao et al., 2024). Specifically, a new absorption band appeared at 425 nm in the visible region, accompanied by a distinct fluorescence emission centred at 535 nm. These features clearly indicate the reappearance of the unmasked parent fluorophore (Fig. 1). Notably, the fluorescence enhancement was also observable under UV illumination, enabling the straightforward visual detection of N₂H₄.

Fluorescence titration studies of ARYA were carried out by gradually adding increasing concentrations of N₂H₄ under optimal conditions. Upon excitation at 435 nm, the emission intensity at 535 nm showed a clear and progressive enhancement, exhibiting a typical "turn-on" response behaviour (Φ_F = 0.11). A strong linear correlation was observed within the N₂H₄ concentration range of 0–200 μ M. The fluorescence intensity reached saturation when approximately 10 equivalents of N₂H₄ were added, leading to a maximum enhancement factor of 35-fold (Fig. 2). Although the initial fluorescence increase occurred rapidly (within 30 seconds), full saturation was typically achieved after 20 minutes (Fig. S5). Rapid response times are particularly desirable for on-site and real-time hydrazine monitoring, where delayed signal generation may limit practical utility (Zeng et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2026).

Based on a regression analysis, the detection limit (LOD) was estimated to be 71 nM (2.3 ppb) (Fig. S6). Compared with previously reported hydrazine probes based on hydrolysis-triggered fluorescence activation, ARYA exhibits a competitive detection limit together with a relatively rapid response under aqueous conditions. Notably, the achieved LOD is comparable to or lower than many reported systems while maintaining operational simplicity (Fan et al., 2022; Jin et al., 2015; Pan et al., 2024; Qin et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2026; Wang et al., 2023; Zeng et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2016). In this context, the advantages of ARYA are clearly illustrated in Table S1, which summarizes its superior features in both aqueous and complex environmental media compared with previously reported N₂H₄ probes.

Since selectivity is a fundamental requirement for the development of reliable fluorescent sensors, the selective response of ARYA toward N₂H₄ was systematically investigated under identical sensing conditions. High selectivity is especially critical for hydrazine detection due to the presence of structurally similar nucleophiles and reducing agents in real samples (Jung et al., 2019; Xiao et al., 2024; Oguz et al., 2024). A broad range of potentially interfering species, including various common metal ions, anions, and biologically relevant small molecules, was tested. Among these, only N₂H₄ was able to induce a significant fluorescence enhancement, consistent with the proposed reaction mechanism involving hydrolysis and ESIPT activation. To further evaluate the potential interference from other analytes, a competitive assay was performed by adding N₂H₄ (10 equiv.) to ARYA in the presence of excess amounts (25 equiv.) of competing species. The fluorescence response remained largely unaffected by the presence of these additives, confirming that ARYA can effectively recognize N₂H₄ with high specificity, even in complex mixtures containing various potentially competing ions and molecules (Fig. 3).

The sensing product was first examined by thin-layer chromatography (TLC), where the appearance of a blue fluorescent spot clearly indicated the formation of starting flavone structure (FL–OH) (Fig. S9). To gain deeper insight into the sensing mechanism of ARYA toward N₂H₄, the reaction between ARYA and N₂H₄ was carried out under the same experimental conditions used for the fluorescence studies. The structural transformation of the probe was monitored ¹H NMR analysis. Upon addition of N₂H₄, distinct changes were observed in the NMR spectrum recorded in d₆-DMSO.

The characteristic proton signals corresponding to the masking

Fig. 4. Partial ^1H NMR spectra of (a) ARYA (b) ARYA + 10 equiv. N_2H_4 (c) FL-OH.

Scheme 2. Proposed mechanism for the detection of N_2H_4 .

Table 1

Results for the detection of N_2H_4 in water samples.

Sample	N_2H_4 spiked (μM)	N_2H_4 found (μM)	Recovery (%)	RSD (%) (n=3)
Drinking water	100.0	101.6 ± 0.80	101.6	0.79
Tap water	100.0	99.6 ± 1.40	99.6	1.41
Wastewater	100.0	105.8 ± 1.60	105.8	1.51

group either shifted (at 7.93 ppm) or disappeared (at 8.30 ppm), indicating successful cleavage of the protective moiety. Simultaneously, new signals appeared at 8.05, 7.47 and 7.36 ppm that were consistent with the regenerated hydroxyaryl structure, confirming the restoration of the ES IPT-active form (Fig. 4). Similar NMR spectral changes accompanying hydrazine-induced deprotection have been reported in closely related sensing systems (Liu et al., 2014). These findings support a mechanism in which N_2H_4 induces a nucleophilic attack on the electrophilic center of the masking group, followed by a rapid hydrolysis step that yields the fluorescent parent compound (Scheme 2).

Encouraged by the excellent analytical performance and fluorescence response of the ARYA probe toward N_2H_4 , we investigated its practical applicability in various real water samples. Application to real matrices is a key criterion for validating the practical relevance of newly developed hydrazine probes (Wang et al., 2023; Zeng et al., 2023; Pan et al., 2024). Given the toxic and carcinogenic nature of N_2H_4 , and its frequent release from industrial activities, developing a simple and accurate detection method is of critical environmental importance. To evaluate the matrix effect, several water samples—including drinking water, tap water and wastewater—were tested without any pretreatment. Known amounts of N_2H_4 were spiked into these samples, and independent calibration curves were constructed for each matrix (Fig. S8).

Despite the presence of potentially interfering substances, the probe exhibited consistent fluorescence responses across all sample types. The recovery values were calculated to be in the range of 99.6–105.8%, with low relative standard deviations (RSDs) between 0.79 and 1.51% (Table 1), confirming the high accuracy and reproducibility of the method. These results collectively demonstrate that ARYA is a robust and reliable probe for the determination of N_2H_4 in complex environmental water samples.

In the next stage of our study, the feasibility of the developed method for detecting N_2H_4 in real environmental matrices was assessed using soil samples. Representative samples of sand, field and clay soil were collected from the Kocaeli region and subjected to oven-drying prior to analysis. A portion of each soil type (200 mg) was spiked with N_2H_4 (200 μM) and introduced into 2 mL of the sensing medium, followed by a two-hour incubation. Subsequently, ARYA was added, and the mixture was gently agitated for an additional 30 minutes. After centrifugation, both N_2H_4 -treated and control samples were imaged under ambient light and UV illumination. Notably, to enhance the visual contrast under UV and

Fig. 5. Detection of N_2H_4 in different soil samples: (a) Daylight images (b) UV light images (366 nm) of soil samples treated with ARYA (40 μM) only, and ARYA (40 μM) + N_2H_4 (200 μM) together in DMSO:PBS (4:1, v/v, pH 7.4).

daylight, the probe concentration was adjusted to 40 μM .

In the presence of N_2H_4 , a distinct colour shift from colourless to pale yellow was clearly observable by the naked eye. Furthermore, while control samples remained non-fluorescent, N_2H_4 -spiked samples exhibited pronounced green fluorescence under UV light (Fig. 5). These results demonstrate the potential of ARYA as a reliable, sensitive, and visually interpretable sensor for N_2H_4 detection in diverse soil environments.

Motivated by the promising sensing performance of ARYA in solution and soil samples, we further evaluated its potential for imaging N_2H_4 in living cells. For this purpose, human lung adenocarcinoma cells (A-549) were first incubated with ARYA (20 μM) for 30 minutes to allow cellular uptake. Subsequently, the cells were treated with N_2H_4 (50 μM) and incubated for an additional 30 minutes. Fluorescence microscopy images were acquired before and after N_2H_4 treatment to monitor intracellular signal changes. Cells treated only with ARYA did not exhibit any fluorescence, indicating that the probe remained in its non-emissive masked form. In contrast, a pronounced fluorescence signal was observed in cells exposed to both ARYA and N_2H_4 , confirming that the probe could permeate the cell membrane and respond selectively to intracellular N_2H_4 (Fig. 6). Furthermore, no morphological abnormalities or signs of cytotoxicity were observed during the experiments, suggesting that ARYA is biocompatible and suitable for in vitro fluorescence imaging applications.

Fig. 6. Images of A-549 cells: (a) Cells were incubated with (a) ARYA (20 μM) in the absence of N_2H_4 (b) cells were incubated with ARYA (20 μM) and N_2H_4 (50 μM) (c) cells are detected with DAPI nuclear counter-stain (control) (d) merged images of the frame (b) and (c) ARYA green, DAPI blue. Scale bars represent 20 μm .

4. Conclusion

A novel ESIPT-based fluorescent probe, ARYA, was rationally designed and synthesized for the selective and sensitive detection of N_2H_4 . The probe exhibited a distinct “turn-on” fluorescence response upon N_2H_4 exposure, accompanied by a visible color change under UV light. Under physiological pH conditions, ARYA remained non-fluorescent due to a blocked hydroxyl group; however, the introduction of N_2H_4 triggered a rapid deprotection reaction, restoring the ESIPT process and generating a strong emission at 535 nm. The probe demonstrated excellent selectivity, a rapid response time (<1 min), and a low detection limit of 71 nM (2.27 ppb). Spectroscopic data, consistent with N_2H_4 -induced hydrolysis and regeneration of the active fluorophore, supported the sensing mechanism. Importantly, ARYA was successfully applied to the determination of N_2H_4 in spiked real water and soil samples as well as in living cells. These results highlight ARYA as a promising fluorescent probe for practical environmental monitoring of N_2H_4 contamination.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Aysenur Cataler Karakus: Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Erman Karakuş:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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